

**МИНИСТЕРСТВО НАУКИ И ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ
РОССИЙСКОЙ ФЕДЕРАЦИИ
ФЕДЕРАЛЬНОЕ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЕ БЮДЖЕТНОЕ
ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЕ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЕ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ**

**«ЧЕЧЕНСКИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ АХМАТА АБДУЛХАМИДОВИЧА КАДЫРОВА»**

Всероссийская молодежная научно-практическая конференция

**«АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ
В ОБЛАСТИ ГЕОГРАФИИ, ЭКОЛОГИИ И ТУРИЗМА»**

7 ноября 2025 г.

Грозный – 2025

УДК 91+504+338.462
ББК 26.8+21.0+65.4

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Актуальные проблемы исследований в области географии, экологии и туризма / Сборник материалов Всероссийской молодежной научно-практической конференции [Электронное издание]: (Грозный, 7 ноября 2025 г.). – Грозный: Издательство ФГБОУ ВО «Чеченский государственный университет им. А.А. Кадырова», 2025. – 194 с.

В материалах Всероссийской молодежной научно-практической конференции «Актуальные проблемы исследований в области географии, экологии и туризма» представлены доклады по следующим направлениям: природно-географические и социально-экономические особенности регионов России, экологические аспекты рационального природопользования и охраны окружающей среды, развитие экологического, этнографического и культурно-познавательного туризма, а также вопросы устойчивого территориального развития и формирования туристско-рекреационных кластеров.

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ISBN 978-5-91127-470-2

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ЭКОГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКАЯ И БИОГЕОХИМИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ПРОЦЕССОВ ОПУСТЫНИВАНИЯ В ГАБАЛИНСКОМ РАЙОНЕ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА

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Аннотация. Процесс опустынивания на территории Габалинского района Азербайджана считается чрезвычайно актуальной как экологической, так и социально-экономической проблемой в условиях всё более засушливых гидрометеорологических и климатических условий. Процесс опустынивания проявляется с разной интенсивностью в зависимости от природных условий территории, особенно антропогенных, рельефных, климатических, биологических и др. Постепенное усиление засух с годами, неравномерное изменение температурно-влажностного режима воздуха, загрязнение почв отходами и перевыпас летних пастбищ продолжают негативно влиять на экологическое равновесие территории. Для оценки прогрессирования опустынивания были применены биогеохимические методы исследования с использованием биогеоценозов, выделенных в пределах естественных ландшафтных фаций. Целью было продемонстрировать ускорение опустынивания на выбранных участках в связи с частыми колебаниями климатической устойчивости и снижением концентрации биодоступных элементов в почве. В данном исследовании также подчеркивается, что процессы опустынивания в Габалинском районе тесно связаны не только с природными факторами, но и с антропогенным воздействием. Вырубка лесов, интенсивный выпас скота, неэффективное землепользование и увеличение объёмов промышленных отходов способствуют снижению плодородия почв и нарушению биогеохимического баланса. Поэтому устойчивое землепользование, усиление экологического мониторинга и повышение осведомлённости местного населения являются важнейшими мерами по снижению рисков опустынивания.

Ключевые слова: биогеохимические особенности, биофильные элементы, процесс опустынивания, Габалинский район, ландшафтные фации, образцы ила.

ECOGEOGRAPHIC AND BIOGEOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DESERTIFICATION PROCESSES IN THE GABALA REGION OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract. The process of desertification in the territory of the Gabala region of Azerbaijan is considered to be an extremely urgent both as an ecological and socio-economic problem, under increasingly arid hydrometeorological and climatic conditions. The process of desertification manifests itself in different intensity depending on the natural conditions of the area, especially anthropogenic, topography, climate, biological, etc. The gradual intensification of drought over the years, indifferent changes in air temperature and humidity regimes, soil pollution by waste, and overgrazing of summer pastures continue to negatively affect the ecological balance of the area. To assess the progression of desertification, biogeochemical research methods were employed, utilizing biogeocenoses defined within natural landscape facies. The aim was to demonstrate the acceleration of desertification in selected sites in connection with frequent shifts in climatic stability and a decline in the concentration of bioavailable elements in the soil. This study also highlights that desertification processes in the Gabala region are closely linked not only to natural factors but also to anthropogenic impacts. Deforestation, intensive grazing, inefficient land use, and the increase of industrial waste contribute to the decline of soil fertility and the disruption of biogeochemical balance. Therefore, sustainable land management, strengthening ecological monitoring, and raising awareness among local communities are essential measures to mitigate the risks of desertification.

Keywords: *biogeochemical features, biophilic elements, desertification process, Gabala region, landscape facies, silt samples.*

1. Introduction

In the territory of Qabala district, the Bumchay, Tikanlichay, Hamzalichay, Damiraparanachay, and Vandamchay rivers form a dense river network. These rivers converge in the southern part of the district to form the Turyanchay River.

In the territory of Gabala district, starting from the watershed of the Great Caucasus range, and entering the Alazan-Haftaran valley and the northern slope of the Sheki plateau, various soil types are present [12, 13].

The studied areas are characterized by the presence of mountain brown forest soils, which are widespread between the Bumchay and Vandamchay basins, at elevations ranging from 1,100 to 2,200 meters above sea level. These soils are notable for a thick forest litter layer, a dark and deep humus horizon, high water retention capacity, significant humus content (8,0–15,0%), and a heavy clayey texture.

Mountain forest-brown soils are distributed in the surrounding areas of the villages of Tikanly, Bum, Hamzali, Zaragan and Vandam at altitudes of 500–1200 m above sea level. Here, forest-brown soils occur in relatively mild and dry climate conditions, under oak forests, shrubs and grasses, in the form of separate glades and strips on the weathering products of carbonate clays. In the territory of the district, in the wide alluvial plain, cut by many branches of Tikanlichay, Bumchay, Hamzalichay, Damiraparanchay and Vandamchay, entering the eastern end of the Alazan-Haftaran valley, alluvial-meadow and some small areas of meadow-swamp land are spread [1, 15].

On the northern slopes of the plateau ridges located here, along with the usual hardened and carbonated, mountain-black soils, dark chestnut and chestnut soils are also spread in small areas.

In all altitude zones, the composition of the primary vegetation cover has changed, it has been disturbed, and they have been replaced by plants of the derivative type.

The climate is basically mild and humid. The amount of abundant sunny days in the area is 2200–2300 hours and the total solar radiation fluctuates between 120–135 kcal/cm². The mild and subtropical climatic conditions are a great resource for the development of subtropical plant growing and husk fruits growing in this area. The favorable natural conditions, climatic characteristics, and soil resources of the Sheki-Zagatala region have led to the emergence of a rich variety of flora and fauna in the Gabala region [11]. Knowing the natural conditions of the region, including its geological and geomorphological structure, and specifying the landscape features play an important role in both the implementation of economic activities and increasing recreational tourism opportunities in the zone.

2. Materials and Methods

Some geomorphological and geological problems of the mountainous terrain exist in Gabala region. It indicates extensive severe erosion, washing, landslides, avalanche processes, flood events and high seismicity. The most extensive mineral raw materials of this region are building materials. Among them are clay (Karkhana, Savalan), which has large reserves in the rocks of the Upper Jurassic and Cretaceous periods, as well as clay shales and sandstones. There are large reserves of river stone, sand and gravel in the catchment areas of the Bumchay, Hamzalichay, Damiraparanchay and Vandamchay rivers. They are used in the production of bricks, ceramic tiles and drainage pipes, as well as in the production of concrete and road construction [12, 14].

As well as in the Sheki-Zagatala region of the southern slope of the Great Caucasus, in the territory of the Gabala region, which is a part of it, research works have been carried out on the landscape facies of the following landscape belts of different types [3, 6].

1. Mountain-forest landscape belt with brown and light brown soils of the middle highlands (1000–1800 m). Test samples – No. 1, 2 and 3.

2. Mountain-forest landscape belt with brown and brown soils of the low mountains (600–1000 m). Test samples – No. 4, 5 and 8.

3. Forest-steppe landscape zone with brown and black soils of the Alazan-Haftaran valley (200–500 m). Test samples – No. 6, 7, 9 and 10.

The methodology formulated by the authors was used to evaluate various landscape facies in landscape monitoring conducted in the Gabala region [9].

I. Alluvial facies group.

1. Alluvial-accumulative facies type.
2. Alluvial-denudation facies type.
3. Denudation-accumulative facies type.
4. Transalluvial facies type.
5. Autonomous-alluvial facies type.
6. Autonomous-denudation facies type.

II. Superaquatic facies group.

1. Trans-accumulative facies type.
2. Erosional-accumulative facies type
3. Erosion-denudation facies type.

III. Subaquatic facies group.

1. Aquatic facies type.
2. Transaquatic facies type.

IV. Delluvial facies group.

1. Delluvial-accumulative facies type.
2. Autonomous-delluvial facies type.

In order to observe the desertification process in the Gabala district of the Sheki-Zagatala region during 2024, landscape monitoring was conducted on April 16, 2024 along the Damiraparanchay River and along the route in the Laza - Savalan direction. On April 26, 2024, landscape diagnostic monitoring was conducted in the landscape boundary - biogeomorphocenosis near the Laza village of Damiraparanchay and silt samples were taken from the river basin [10]. The coordinates of the silt and soil samples are shown in *map-scheme 1* and *table 1*.

Map-scheme 1. Physical map of Gabala region. Areas where soil and sludge samples were taken are shown on the map.

Soil samples were also taken from a number of different forest and grassland landscape types during the monitoring. All soil and silt samples were prepared for subsequent chemical analysis to determine the amount of biophilic macro and microelements.

Analyzing the amount of a number of biophilic elements in silt and soil samples is of great importance in determining their role in biogeochemical activation in landscape facies [5]. For example, the element N (nitrogen) plays a very important role in biogenic cycles, as this cycle is related to the nitrogen cycle in both the atmosphere and water basins. Diffusion activation zones environ the processes of natural diffusion and dispersion of chemicals. The element P (Phosphorus) often acts as a major nutrient for plants and microorganisms, and is also found in stratigraphy in its mineral form as phosphates. Oxidation-reduction (redox) reactions are widespread processes in landscape facies with different climatic and relief conditions. The element Fe (iron) plays a key role in such activations, since iron can be oxidized or reduced, which leads to changes in the biogeochemical environment in soils. The element C (carbon), which expresses the amount of humus in soils contribute significantly to the circulation of carbonate and organic substances. Hydrodynamic activation in waters due to the influence of increasing CO in the atmosphere in connection with global climate change results in the activation of water flows and erosion. The process of desertification in landscape facies is characterized by enrichment with Na against the background of a decrease in the K element in the biogeochemical environment [2]. The normal amount of K entering the Earth's landscape sphere is only related to neotectonic movements and magmatic activities in the Earth's crust. Geochemical changes in this process can lead to the formation of new minerals and chemical elements.

As a result of the landscape diagnostic studies conducted, it was determined that the desertification process in the Gabala region depends mainly on the semi-arid climate and plateau relief conditions in the Amirvan plateau and the Turyanchay valley in the southern part of the region.

In the areas located on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus Range (between the settlements of Bum - Gabala - Vandam) in the Gabala region, the desertification process is manifested with greater intensity, depending on the anthropological factor.

The chemical composition of the silt and soil samples submitted for chemical analysis to the laboratory of the Sheki Regional Center of the Agrarian Services Agency is given in Table 1.

Table 1.

Chemical composition of silt and soil samples taken from the territory of Gabala region

№	Examples and locations	Indicators	Unit of measure	Analysis result	Norm	Evaluation
1.	Gabala region. Damiraparanchay, Upper Turbaza. Sandy-silt. Absolute altitude-1200 m. N – 41.00.58. E – 47.53.40.	pH	-	9.06	6.6–7.5	Strongly alkaline
		Salinity	mS/cm	0.169	0–2	Non-Salt
		Humus	%	0.12	2–3	Very weak
		P ₂ O ₅	kg/ha	49.22	60–120	Weak
		K ₂ O	kg/ha	76.5	250–550	Very weak
		Na	mg/kg	30.9	81–120	Very weak
		N	%	0.006	0.09–0.17	Very weak
		Fe	mg/kg	10.9	2.5–4.5	High
		Lime	%	19.7	5–15	High
		Mn	mg/kg	7	14–50	Weak
		Cu	mg/kg	1.2	≥ 0.2	Adequate
Zn	mg/kg	0.36	1.0–2.4	Weak		
2	Gabala region. Damiraparanchay, Lower Turbaza. Sandy-silt. Absolute altitude- 1100 m. N – 40.59.12.	pH	-	8.06	6.6–7.5	Weak alkaline
		Salinity	mS/cm	0.133	0–2	Non-Salt
		Humus	%	0.29	2–3	Very weak
		P ₂ O ₅	kg/ha	14.88	60–120	Very weak
		K ₂ O	kg/ha	76.5	250–550	Very weak
		Na	mg/kg	14.8	81–120	Very weak
		N	%	0.014	0.09–0.17	Very weak

	E – 47.51.59.	Fe	mg/kg	18.72	2.5–4.5	High
		Lime	%	4.8	5–15	Weak
		Mn	mg/kg	1.688	14–50	Very weak
		Cu	mg/kg	1.072	≥ 0.2	Adequate
		Zn	mg/kg	0.936	1.0–2.4	Weak
3	Gabala region. Damiraparanchay. Gabala – Baku highway. Sandy-silt. Absolute altitude – 1000 m N – 40.57.15. E – 47.51.52	pH	-	7.95	6.6–7.5	Weak alkaline
		Salinity	mS/cm	0.154	0–2	Non-Salt
		Humus	%	0.92	2–3	Very weak
		P ₂ O ₅	kg/ha	14.88	60–120	Very weak
		K ₂ O	kg/ha	69.9	250–550	Very weak
		Na	mg/kg	18.0	81–120	Very weak
		N	%	0.046	0.09–0.17	Weak
		Fe	mg/kg	19.44	2.5–4.5	High
		Lime	%	4.4	5–15	Weak
		Mn	mg/kg	1.664	14–50	Very weak
		Cu	mg/kg	0.784	≥ 0.2	Adequate
		Zn	mg/kg	0.656	1.0–2.4	Weak
4	Gabala region. Zaraghan village. Gabala – Baku highway. The soil. Absolute altitude – 650 m. N – 40.55.44. E – 47.47.00.	pH	-	7.75	6.6–7.5	Weak alkaline
		Salinity	mS/cm	0.371	0–2	Non-Salt
		Humus	%	1.6	2–3	Weak
		P ₂ O ₅	kg/ha	33.2	60–120	Weak
		K ₂ O	kg/ha	448.5	250–550	Medium
		Na	mg/kg	26.6	81–120	Very weak
		N	%	0.08	0.09–0.17	Weak
		Fe	mg/kg	23.128	2.5–4.5	High
		Lime	%	4.6	5–15	Weak
		Mn	mg/kg	2.632	14–50	Very weak
		Cu	mg/kg	3.424	≥ 0.2	Adequate
		Zn	mg/kg	0.928	1.0–2.4	Weak
5.	Gabala region. Vandamchay. Gabala – Baku highway. Sandy-silt. Absolute altitude-800 m. N – 40.57.09. E – 47.55.57.	pH	-	8.76	6.6–7.5	Strongly alkaline
		Salinity	mS/cm	0.203	0–2	Non-Salt
		Humus	%	1.87	2–3	Weak
		P ₂ O ₅	kg/ha	8.575	60–120	Very weak
		K ₂ O	kg/ha	105	250–550	Very weak
		Na	mg/kg	10.4	81–120	Very weak
		N	%	0.093	0.09–0.17	Medium
		Fe	mg/kg	12.01	2.5–4.5	High
		Lime	%	10.4	5–15	Medium
		Mn	mg/kg	7.4	14–50	Weak
		Cu	mg/kg	1.7	≥ 0.2	Adequate
		Zn	mg/kg	0.74	1.0–2.4	Weak
6.	Gabala region. Damiraparanchay. Charkhana village. Sandy-silt. Absolute altitude-220 m. N – 40.47.48. E – 47.37.54.	pH	-	8.54	6.6–7.5	Weak alkaline
		Salinity	mS/cm	0.592	0–2	Non-Salt
		Humus	%	1.02	2–3	Weak
		P ₂ O ₅	kg/ha	5.075	60–120	Very weak
		K ₂ O	kg/ha	87	250–550	Very weak
		Na	mg/kg	77.2	81–120	Weak
		N	%	0.051	0.09–0.17	Weak
		Fe	mg/kg	14.4	2.5–4.5	High
		Lime	%	6.32	5–15	Medium
		Mn	mg/kg	8.4	14–50	Weak
		Cu	mg/kg	3.3	≥ 0.2	Adequate
		Zn	mg/kg	0.55	1.0–2.4	Weak
7.	Gabala region.	pH	-	8.67	6.6–7.5	Strongly alkaline

	Turyanchay. Savalan village. Sandy-silt. Absolute altitude-180 m. N – 40.46.39. E – 47.36.20.	Salinity	mS/cm	0.984	0–2	Non-salty
		Humus	%	0.87	2–3	Very weak
		P ₂ O ₅	kg/ha	4.95	60–120	Very weak
		K ₂ O	kg/ha	103.75	250–550	Very weak
		Na	mg/kg	255.7	81–120	Very high
		N	%	0.043	0.09–0.17	Very weak
		Fe	mg/kg	13.1	2.5–4.5	High
		Lime	%	7.04	5–15	Medium
		Mn	mg/kg	10.6	14–50	Weak
		Cu	mg/kg	1.9	≥ 0.2	Adequate
		Zn	mg/kg	0.64	1.0–2.4	Weak
8	Gabala region. Hamzalichay. Sandy- silt. Absolute altitude-600 m. N – 40.55.32 E – 47.44.21	pH	-	7.48	6.6–7.5	Neutral
		Salinity	mS/cm	0.281	0–2	Non-salty
		Humus	%	0.18	2–3	Very weak
		P ₂ O ₅	kg/ha	10.3	60–120	Very weak
		K ₂ O	kg/ha	76.5	250–550	Very weak
		Na	mg/kg	14.8	81–120	Very weak
		N	%	0.009	0.09–0.17	Very weak
		Fe	mg/kg	17.2	2.5–4.5	High
		Lime	%	10.6	5–15	Medium
		Mn	mg/kg	1.368	14–50	Very weak
		Cu	mg/kg	1.008	≥ 0.2	Adequate
Zn	mg/kg	0.768	1.0–2.4	Weak		
9	Oguz region. Bayan village. The soil. Absolute altitude-400 m. N – 41.02.20. E – 47.26.16.	pH	-	7.43	6.6–7.5	Neutral
		Salinity	mS/cm	0.17	0–2	Non-salty
		Humus	%	3.53	2–3	High
		P ₂ O ₅	kg/ha	79.57	60–120	Medium
		K ₂ O	kg/ha	649.2	250–550	High
		Na	mg/kg	22	81–120	Very weak
		N	%	0.176	0.09–0.17	High
		Fe	mg/kg	34.32	2.5–4.5	High
		Lime	%	1.04	5–15	Weak
		Mn	mg/kg	6.472	14–50	Weak
		Cu	mg/kg	4.88	≥ 0.2	Adequate
Zn	mg/kg	1.104	1.0–2.4	Medium		
10	Oghuz region. Filfili village. The soil. Absolute altitude-500 m. N – 41.03.55. E – 47.32.30.	pH	-	7.21	6.6–7.5	Neutral
		Salinity	mS/cm	0.35	0–2	Non-salty
		Humus	%	8.48	2–3	Very high
		P ₂ O ₅	kg/ha	32.63	60–120	Weak
		K ₂ O	kg/ha	611.1	250–550	High
		Na	mg/kg	11.6	81–120	Very weak
		N	%	0.424	0.09–0.17	Very high
		Fe	mg/kg	39.84	2.5–4.5	High
		Lime	%	19.2	5–15	High
		Mn	mg/kg	2.264	14–50	Very weak
		Cu	mg/kg	2.064	≥ 0.2	Adequate
Zn	mg/kg	6.184	1.0–2.4	High		

Naturally, soil has various chemical, physical and biological properties related to plant growth and the environment. The given elements and indicators are important in terms of determining the composition and productivity of the soil. Information about the biogeochemical nature and role of the chemical elements shown below in the soil is given:

The pH indicator of the soil shows its level of acidity or alkalinity. Soil pH is closely related to plant nutrition. When the pH is too low (acidic) or too high (basic), some important nutrients (such

as phosphorus and nitrogen) become insoluble in the soil and are difficult for plants to absorb. The optimal pH value for most plants is between 6.0 and 7.5.

The concentration of salts in the soil, especially the concentration of sodium, potassium and magnesium ions, affects on the water retention capacity of the soil and the nutritional conditions of plants. High salinity can inhibit the development of plant root systems and make it difficult to absorb water. High salinity can lead to poor soil quality and crop losses in agricultural areas.

Humus is a substance formed as a result of the decomposition of organic matter in the soil, which increases the structure and fertility of the soil. It helps retain water in the soil, develop microorganisms, and make nutrients available in the soil. Humus increases the microbiological activity of the soil and regulates the pH of the soil.

Phosphorus is an essential element for plants because it is included in the composition of cell walls, genetic materials and energy carriers. The amount of phosphorus in the soil directly affects plant growth. Lack of phosphorus slows down plant development. Phosphorus is largely immobile in the soil, making it difficult for plants to obtain this element.

Potassium is an essential nutrient for plants and is important in increasing cell density, regulating water and acidity. Potassium also participates in photosynthesis and protein synthesis. When potassium is available in sufficient quantities in the soil, plants grow more robustly and healthily.

Although sodium does not directly affect plant growth, it causes a saline environment in the soil. Too much sodium in the soil can make it difficult to absorb other nutrients. Too much sodium can limit plant growth and cause salinity problems in the soil.

Nitrogen is a major nutrient for plants and is essential for their growth and development. Nitrogen is included in the composition of proteins, amino acids and other vital substances. Nitrogen deficiency can cause slow growth and yellowing of plants. The availability of nitrogen in the soil is ensured by soil microorganisms.

Iron is an essential micronutrient for plants, as it is required for photosynthesis and the transport of oxygen to cells. The uptake of iron by plants depends on the pH value. Iron deficiency can cause yellowing and a weakness in the photosynthesis process in plants.

Lime (CaCO_3) raises the pH of the soil and improves soil structure. Calcium enters the cell walls. Calcium is essential for healthy plant growth. Having enough calcium in the soil has a positive effect on plant health. It also regulates the availability of other nutrients in the soil.

Magnesium is an important trace element for plants and is contained in chlorophyll. Chlorophyll is the main element for photosynthesis, and the presence of magnesium enhances the photosynthetic activity of plants. Magnesium deficiency can cause yellowing in plants and a weakening of the photosynthesis process.

Copper is one of the micronutrients important for plants, but present in small amounts. It helps in the action of enzymes and is necessary for the growth of plants. Copper deficiency can slow plant growth and make plants more susceptible to disease.

Zinc is a trace element essential for plant growth and development. It participates in the activity of enzymes, plant photosynthesis, and plays a role in the synthesis of genetic material. Zinc deficiency leads to growth retardation and deformation in plants. These chemical indicators are the main factors that ensure the ecosystem functions and productivity of the soil. The composition of the soil and the amount of these elements affect the growth, development, and productivity of plants.

Manganese is an important micronutrient for plants and is involved in many enzyme activities. It also plays an important role in photosynthesis, energy production, and antioxidant activities. Manganese also plays a role in plant cellular respiration and protein synthesis. Manganese deficiency can result in stunted growth, yellowing, and reduced photosynthetic activity in plants. High manganese concentrations can cause toxicity in plants.

3. Results and Discussion

As can be seen from Table 1, the following regularities were found in the sludge samples taken along the middle streams of Demiraparanchay and Vandamchay:

1. Silt substrates are usually characterized by alkaline environmental conditions with pH values ≥ 8.0 .

2. The amount of the assimilated Fe element is also found in very high quantities.
3. The amount of humus, phosphorus, nitrogen and assimilated Mn and Zn elements in the silt substrate is significantly lower than the norm.
4. In most cases, the amount of carbonation and Cu element in the silt substrate is represented at an average level.
5. While the amount of Na element is lower than the norm in the upper and middle reaches of the Damiraparanchay, which corresponds to a semi-humid climate, it is sharply higher than the norm in the Turyanchay area, which has semi-arid climatic conditions (Fig 1).

Fig 1. Change in Na element indicators in sandy-silty sediments of the Damiraparanchay basin with decreasing absolute altitude.

The graphical indicators of pH, Na, Lime and Fe in sandy-silt and soil samples of Gabala and Oghuz regions are given in Figure No. 1–5.

According to Table 1, the following regularities were identified in the silt samples as they descended along the Damiraparanchay and Vandamchay riverbeds:

1. The amount of salinity (mS/cm) is approaching the normal limits from low values, while the amount of lime (in % carbonate content), on the contrary, is significantly decreasing from the normal in this direction (Fig 2).

Fig 2. Change in lime indicators in sandy-silty sediments of the Damiraparanchay basin with decreasing absolute height.

2. As the Damiraparanchay and Vandamchay rivers descend along the riverbed, the alkalinity-acidity indicators in the sludge samples are usually $\text{pH} \geq 8.0$, which is due to the leaching of alkaline elements (Na, Ca, K, Mg, etc.) from floodplains in high mountainous areas (Fig 3).

Fig 3. Change in pH values in sandy-silty sediments of the Damiraparanchay basin with decreasing absolute altitude.

3. The decrease in the ratio of carbonation to salinity indicates an intensification of the desertification process in the area [7, 8].

4. Since the amount of K and P elements assimilated in the silt samples is much lower than the norm, the siltation of agricultural fields as a result of floods and floods creates serious difficulties for farm work.

5. The amount of the nitrogen element close to the norm allows for a period of time the cultivation of nitrogen-loving plants in soils silted up by floods and floods.

6. As the Damiraparanchay and Vandamchay rivers descend along the riverbed, the amount of Fe absorbed in the silt samples is significantly higher than normal, the amount of Cu is sufficient, and the amount of Mn and Zn is lower than normal (Fig 4 and 5).

Fig 4. Change in Fe element indicators in sandy-silty sediments of the Damiraparanchay basin with decreasing absolute altitude.

Fig 5. Change in Fe indicators in soil samples from Gabala and Oghuz regions with decreasing absolute altitude.

7. Over time, this sludge material became earthy and increased the content of humus and humus-related biophilic elements such as K, P, Mn, Cu, and Zn, and decreased the parameters of carbonate, salinity, and alkalinity.

8. When comparing the chemical composition of silt samples from the Damiraparanchay river beds of Gabala region and Dashagilchay river beds of Oguz region, it is revealed that the former has a more alkaline environment. This may be related to the increased erosion of flood hotspots in the Damiraparanchay basin [4, 8].

4. Conclusion

In the territory of Gabala region, the desertification process is manifested with greater intensity in the Amirvan plateau in the southern part and partly in the Turyanchay valley, depending on the climatic conditions, and on the southern slope of the Main Caucasus Range (in the area between the villages of Nij and Vandam) depending on the anthropological factor. Therefore, while the amount

of Na element is below the norm in the upper and middle reaches of the Damiraparanchay, which corresponds to the semi-humid climate, it has sharply increased above the norm in the Turyanchay area, which has semi-arid climatic conditions.

As the Damiraparanchay and Vandamchay rivers descend, the alkalinity-acidity indicators in the sludge samples are usually $\text{pH} \geq 8.0$, which is due to the leaching out of alkaline elements (Na, Ca, K, Mg, etc.) in the high mountainous areas and the accumulation of the element Fe. For this reason, the ratio of carbonation to salinity in the sludge samples decreases, which indicates that the desertification process is intensifying in the southern plateau area.

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Всероссийская молодежная научно-практическая конференция

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В ОБЛАСТИ ГЕОГРАФИИ, ЭКОЛОГИИ И ТУРИЗМА»**

Подписано в печать 02.12.2025 г. Формат 60x84/8
Бумага офисная. Печать-ризография.
Уч.-изд. л. 14,2. Тираж 100 экз.

Издательство Чеченского государственного университета им. А.А. Кадырова
Адрес: 364037 ЧР, г. Грозный, ул. Субры Кишиевой, 33